

23. Agroforestry in the next EU Research Framework Programme (2025-2027)

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The European Agroforestry Federation is an NGO (Transparency Register [913270437706-82](https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/regexp10/index.cfm?do=entity.entity_details&entity_id=913270437706-82)), which “promotes the adoption of agroforestry practices across Europe by supporting efforts to develop awareness, education, research, policy making and investments which foster the use of trees on farms”. It has a network of 31 affiliated entities in 23 countries.

This document is produced by the EURAF Scientific Committee as a short contribution to the [EU consultation on the “past, present and future of European Research and Innovation Programmes 2014-2027”](#) It will be updated periodically: for example, to reflect the conclusions of EURAF’s next bi-annual conference in June 2024. (see Policy [Briefing #16](#) for a summary of the 2022 Conference).

1. Introduction

The European Agroforestry Federation (euraf.net) aims to promote the adoption of agroforestry practices throughout Europe, by increasing information and awareness among professionals and the general public, supporting to support education and research, and working towards policy frameworks which promote the use of trees and edible shrubs on farms in Europe.

10 pathways to achieve the four key food and nutrition goals. Source: [Food 2030, European Commission](#)

Agroforestry (AF) can be defined as “the practice of deliberately integrating woody vegetation (trees or shrubs) with crop and/or animal systems to support the conservation, benefit from the resulting ecological and economic interactions”, although a range of definitions are applied by Member States in their CAP Strategic Plans ([EURAF Policy Briefing #22](#))¹ The benefits of agroforestry practices and systems are widely recognised by the **European and international research community, policy makers, farming community or intergovernmental organisations** (e.g. FAO – Food and Agriculture Organisation)¹. AF is an ancient agricultural practice², being a set of nature-based solutions inspired by agroecology which are integrated nowadays in various educational university programmes as a multidisciplinary branch of science (e.g. agronomy, forestry, landscape ecology, etc).

In addition to bridging the gap between policy making, academia and the farming community ([EURAF](#) develops policy briefings on key EU pieces of legislation), EURAF strongly supports research on AF. Currently, it is a project partner in four Horizon Framework programme projects ([DigitAF](#), [DISTENDER](#), [ResAlliance](#), [CREDIBLE](#))³ and its members have been participants in a wide range of EU funded initiatives – such as those under the 7th Framework Programme (FP7 [AgForward](#), [SAFE](#)) and Horizon 2020 ([AFINET](#), [AgroMix](#), [MIXED](#), [FIRE-RES](#), etc.)⁴.

¹Agroforestry has two main categories: silvoarable (trees in alleys or sparsely cultivated with crops) and (agro)silvopastoral where trees are combined with livestock (and possibly crops).

²Cato the Younger and Pliny the elder wrote about mixtures of trees and crops more than 2000 years ago.

³ EURAF members are also involved in other projects, such as: eco2adapt, AF4EU, ReForest, etc.

⁴ EURAF estimates that about 40 projects have been funded since 2015 (e.g. through Horizon, Life, Interreg calls).

EURAF considers this public consultation a matter of key importance and has initiated an *internal scientific committee* to provide inputs. Building on past EU funded projects and scientific publications, a series of activities were organised ahead of drafting this document:

- collecting **feedback from experts** affiliated to EURAF (through surveys);
- reviewing the **scientific literature**⁵, organised in line with recognised academic criteria;
- identifying the **knowledge gaps** highlighted by this literature review⁶;
- prioritising topics for **future research and innovation projects** - which would maximise the contribution of AF to meet the EU's agricultural and environmental objectives (i.e. EU Green Deal).

EURAF's Scientific Committee identified *four priorities* which may assist the future strategic orientations of Horizon Europe (2025-2027). Topics are defined in line with the [key objectives of the programme](#) (i.e. maximising scientific, technological, economic and societal impacts), as well with the [Food 2030 initiative](#) and the [FAO Science and Innovation Strategy](#). The priorities are:

- 2.1. Empowering the farming community to make a bolder contribution towards EU's environmental and climate targets;
- 2.2. Developing a toolbox to strengthen the links between researchers, AF practitioners and communities;
- 2.3. Improving EU's food, fibre and energy self-sufficiency;
- 2.4. Accelerating the transition from 'silo thinking' to a multidimensional view of food production, while bridging the gap between science and practice.

2. Research and innovation priorities

2.1 Empowering the farming community to make a bolder contribution towards EU's environmental and climate targets;

In the context of EU's environmental and climate targets (e.g. EU Farm to Fork, EU Biodiversity Strategy - and the overarching EU Green Deal), EURAF believes that future research and innovation initiatives should play a more important role in **better equipping the farming community** to tackle current and imminent challenges. Future EU-funded projects may:

- A. Support long-term experiments capitalising on experimental networks conducted at biogeographic area level. In the context of the increasing pressure of climate change events, knowledge transfer between different biogeographic areas should be facilitated/accelerated^{2,3}. Future research should further fill knowledge gaps regarding the **distribution of water in AF** (e.g. how it is shared between crops and trees) and to what extent additional irrigation may be beneficial or not for the development of specific AF systems and their productivity⁴.
- B. Harmonise tools for **mapping trees outside** of forests (ToF) - particularly in the context of the proposed EU Regulation on Forest Monitoring and Strategic Planning (see EURAF [Policy Briefing #15](#)). Classification of accounting for trees in intentional and unintentional agroforestry^{5,6} is necessary. The implications for mechanised arable operations, long-term timber values and the effect of trees on land value should be investigated (as well as suggestions made by farmers for the tree component⁷).
- C. Disseminate action-oriented knowledge on the benefits of AF (e.g. silvoarable) in the context of **Integrated Pest Management (IPM)** practices^{8,9} and **address/tackle bottlenecks** that impede the implementation of such AF-based IPM strategies (in view of reducing the use of synthetic pesticides).
- D. Build on existing EU Mission Soil initiatives and promote a holistic approach when evaluating or modelling **SOC stocks and processes**^{10,11} including the role of AF practices in soil formation and their role on the net balance of greenhouse gases.
- E. Methods for **sampling and accounting** should be standardised⁵. There is a need to understand the driving factors for SOC storage in agroforestry (e.g. agrosilvopastoral systems), particularly in subsoils (e.g. where substances such as nitrates are actively absorbed by living roots¹², where information is scarce Cardinael et al¹³ recommended '*synthesising data from local field experiments to generate country-specific factors*' for the C sequestration potential of AF), as well as the impact of land conversion to AF on soil properties¹⁴.

⁵ Most publications reported in this document refer to the period 2017-2023.

⁶ This process was also conducted building on the 'research needs' identified by the EIP-AGRI Focus Group on Agroforestry - [December, 2017](#).

- F. Provide insights into the **trade-off between radiation decrease and microclimate** improvements in intercropped systems with summer crops ^{4,15}
- G. Research on more efficient **nutrient management practices**. ¹⁶ put forward three specific recommendations in this regard: the adaptation of fertilisation rates, the optimisation of nutrient inputs both in space and time and the diversification of crops.
- H. Concerning modelling, research and innovation should focus on **modular, freely accessible and re-usable frameworks** in which tree growth (e.g. above ground biomass - ¹⁷, crop growth, and components account for species competition ¹⁵.

2.2 Developing a toolbox to strengthen the links between researchers, AF practitioners and communities.

Building on the good practices developed by previous national/EU-funded initiatives (e.g. living labs, stakeholders training, field demonstrations), EURAF members consider that the role of communities is crucial in streamlining multi stakeholder knowledge transfer¹⁸. Additionally, strengthening ties with communities (both LAU level 1 and 2) bring numerous benefits with regards to the implementation and durability of such projects on a wider landscape scale (as collaboration between landowners and local authorities is beneficial in tackling bottlenecks from implementation and throughout the lifetime of agroforests). Future EU-funded projects may support **multi actor research and innovation** on developing tools to:

- A. Further raise awareness regarding the role of AF in **diversifying farmers' streams of revenue** by incentivising the co-production of innovative (agricultural) goods in woody strips or around orchards (such as 'chicken-pastured orchards', which have reciprocal benefits for both trees and animals - ¹⁹. This is an opportunity to optimise the provisioning service of the tree component and diversify the agricultural production ²⁰ – but also in developing **shorter supply chains** at community or regional level (by incentivising niche farming practices such the production of berries, mushrooms, herbs, or edible tree species - as implemented in the 'edible forest gardens' concept - see ²¹.
- B. Measure and monitor the role of AF in **climate regulation** ^{5,15}, effects on the **microclimate** (through shading or wind protection ¹⁷ **and water balance** from field-scale to the landscape scale AF e.g. agrosilvopastoral ²².
- C. Model and assess the potential of silvopastoralism in **reducing wildfires' risk** – while better quantifying economic savings from the prevented destruction ^{23,24}; in line with relevant climate models. Further develop methods and tools to facilitate knowledge transfer at different policy and technical levels (e.g. land-use planning).
- D. Further raise awareness regarding the benefits of AF in the context of **biodiversity enhancement** ²⁵ or the implementation of AF as part of the Trans-European Nature Network of **ecological corridors**;
- E. Develop **landscape strategies** to use AF in restoring degraded areas, around urban and rural communities, or in the context of renewable energy projects (e.g. agri photovoltaic systems²⁶)

2.3 Improving EU's food, fibre and energy self-sufficiency

In the context of the current global challenges (e.g. post-COVID recovery, geopolitical tensions, increasing frequency of climate change-related events, etc.), the subject of food sovereignty becomes of paramount importance⁷. Future EU-funded projects may:

- A. **Improve access to action-oriented AF knowledge** (e.g. clearly defining key AF terminology and basic methodologies, such as the 'land equivalent ratio'), by ensuring that educational tools (e.g. manuals, project results, digitalised support, virtual/augmented reality ²⁷ on AF practices are available, accessible and adaptable to various biogeographic conditions, while expanding the **toolbox to assess and optimise AF production performance** in terms of quality, safety and sustainability.
- B. **Promote research on of crop varieties** that are highly adaptable to changing environmental conditions e.g. shade-tolerant crops ^{16,28}, salt-tolerant trees or crops, etc. and their use in different biogeographic regions;
- C. Fill knowledge gaps regarding the connections between **variable climate conditions** and yield ²⁹.
- D. Explore **synergistic crop-tree interactions** in view of reducing/mitigating the inhibitory impact of allelopathic chemicals ⁴ - and maximise productivity on land ³⁰.
- E. In terms of **genetics**, broadening quantitative knowledge on the performance of different crops when competing for resources with trees hinders the adoption of silvoarable systems ²⁸.

⁷ https://commission.europa.eu/system/files/2023-01/SWD_2023_4_1_EN_document_travail_service_part1_v2.pdf

- F. Study and develop resource-efficient nature-based/-inspired business models (e.g. relying on agroecological, AF or organic practices), while better understanding the biodiversity - climate - health nexus.
- G. Mainstream good AF practices that contribute to **enhancing local biodiversity**^{2,31}, while further exploring the potential of AF (e.g. grazing) in the **management of invasive and opportunistic species**³².
- H. Fill knowledge gaps on the use of fodder tree species (in livestock diets - e.g.³³ may contribute to **maximising the circularity potential of AF**, while also **reducing the feed-food competition**³⁴. Build on the preliminary evidence indicating correlations between the use of fodder tree in livestock diets and the reduction of internal parasite infestation³⁵ or the inhibition of methanogenesis³⁶.
- I. Advance the knowledge of how silvopastoral practices and the use of fodder tree species benefit **animal welfare indicators**, feeding behaviour and productivity^{33,37}.

2.4 Accelerating the transition from silo thinking to a multidimensional view around food production, while bridging the gap between science and practice.

Taking stock of the various publications on sustainable agricultural practices, such as agroecology, organic farming, AF, etc. EURAF believes that initiatives such as living labs, stakeholders' training, field demonstrations, innovation clusters or platforms, citizen science activities, etc. could play a key role in making the communication and knowledge transfer between the scientific and farming communities more efficient – in view of maximising the impact of the multifunctional benefits of AF (e.g. social, economic, cultural, etc.^{38,39}. Future EU-funded projects may:

- A. **Better quantify** the public as well as private benefits of silvoarable systems while engaging in a **truly multi-stakeholder process** (e.g. engage with farmers and address 'issues that farmers see as important', as recommended by⁷. There is a need to revisit the on-farm economics of AF demonstration sites⁷.
- B. Research on **productivity and economics** (e.g. cost-benefit analysis) to fill gaps on how AF has advantages in years with lower yields than usual (e.g. droughts, pests, etc.) or clarify to what extent the revenue from trees compensates for the modest overall decrease in crop yield in the first years of establishment^{10,28}.
- C. **Develop and promote participatory research strategies**, integrated with remote sensing and multi-temporal analysis of land use changes. These should focus on acknowledging and preserving AF as **rural historic landscapes** - while enhancing the role of the traditional agricultural heritage in socio-economic and environmental terms (addressing the strong interconnection between environment - agricultural practices - and various socio-economic matters^{23,40–42}.

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